

Mobilizing microbial data: Insights from a ELIXIR Pathogen Data Focus Group and ELIXIR Microbiome Community Workshop (ELIXIR All Hands Meeting 2025)

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Abstract

Microbial molecular data is vital for studying pathogens, microbiomes, and their influence on health, the environment, and global challenges, such as antibiotic resistance and climate change. Yet, managing, preserving, sharing, and reusing these data remains challenging due to missing or inconsistent metadata and poorly integrated data systems. To address this, the ELIXIR Pathogen Data Focus Group and the Microbiome Community held a joint workshop during the ELIXIR All Hands Meeting 2025 in Thessaloniki. Participants discussed what metadata is most useful, what data/metadata can be shared early, and how to improve data quality. Solutions included better incentives, training, automation, and the use of AI tools. The workshop produced recommendations for more effective microbial data sharing.

Introduction

Advances in sequencing and molecular profiling have led to an enormous growth in microbial data across clinical, environmental, and agricultural domains [1], [2]. Despite this, mobilizing data in ways that enable timely sharing, integration, and reuse remains a significant challenge. Practices have been developed in isolation across disciplines, inconsistent or domain-specific metadata standards, limited use of controlled vocabularies, and insufficient incentives and tooling for metadata capture collectively impede efforts to make microbial data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) [3] [4].

To address these issues, a joint workshop was organized by the ELIXIR Pathogen Data Focus Group (PDFG) and the ELIXIR Microbiome Community (MC) [5] during the ELIXIR All Hands Meeting 2025. While the PDFG concentrates on pathogen genomics in a One Health context, the MC works more broadly on microbial communities across diverse biomes [5]. Despite these different scopes, both groups share a strong commitment to data stewardship and management, standardization, and improvement of discoverability through aligned metadata practices.

The workshop aimed to identify cross-cutting challenges and develop actionable recommendations for improved data interoperability. Through a combination of expert presentations and collaborative group discussions, participants examined shared use cases and explored practical solutions to bridge gaps between technical infrastructures and scientific domains. Outcomes from the workshop contribute to shaping a more unified approach to microbial data sharing across Europe's life science infrastructure.

Part I: Metadata identification

It is common that research studies produce much richer contextual metadata than the data repositories minimally require. Further, it is standard practice not to share data until the related scientific publication is accepted. To give the workshop context, the first session started with a presentation on "Metadata standards in sequence archives: ENA metadata model" by Joana Pauperio (EMBL-EBI). The talk covered sample and metadata models, ENA checklists, and metadata standards. It also covered the post-submission curation of metadata through the Data Clearing House.

The presentation was followed by a group work session, where the objectives were to:

1. Identify what metadata are needed to conduct studies beyond the mandatory (minimal) elements required by the final repository. Do they exist in checklists?
2. Identify what types of metadata it might be possible to make public prior to publication, in order to allow early discovery of data?

To facilitate the collection of feedback and shared experiences from participants, the key questions were addressed using pre-made spreadsheets with controlled vocabulary (Table 1).

Table 1 - Metadata requirements survey questions and their possible options

Questions	Possible Options
Data producer - Submitting data to public repositories	
Data type	Genomic isolates, Metagenomics, Transcriptomics, Proteomics, Amplicon, Multi-Locus Sequence Typing (MLST) <i>Multiple choices possible</i>
Organism group	Bacteria, Viruses, Eukaryotes <i>Multiple choices possible</i>
Scientific application area	Human health, Agriculture, Aquaculture, Wastewater surveillance, Food Safety, Environmental Microbiology, Zoonotic Disease Surveillance, Outbreak Investigation <i>Multiple choices possible</i>
Purpose of data production	AMR gene association studies, Vaccine candidate development, Gene expression profiling, Pathogen protein characterization, Community profiling, Strain typing and clustering, Variant Tracking, Comparative Genomics, Diagnostic Tool Development, Training Machine Learning Models <i>Multiple choices possible</i>
Public repository for your data	ENA, GenBank, Swiss Prot, PRIDE, PeptideAtlas, MGnify, Qiita, PubMLST, EnteroBase, GISAID, PATRIC, BioSamples, ArrayExpress, SRA* <i>Multiple choices possible</i>
Would you feel comfortable exposing part of the metadata at sample level or only aggregated information for the whole dataset prior to publication?	Only aggregated data, Only selected metadata at sample level, Both aggregated and sample level information
Sample level: Metadata you would allow for early discovery (pre-publication)	Free text

Aggregated level: Information you would share for early discovery (pre-publication)	Free text
ENA checklist	Select from https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/checklists
MixS checklist	MigsBa, MigsEu, MigsOrg, MigsPI, MigsVi, Mimag, MimarksC, MimarksS, Mims, Misag, Miuvig, Other - extensions
Other checklists	Free text
Do you have access to contextual data from the wet lab (e.g., protocols for data generation [info like SARS-CoV-2 ARTIC Network Protocol])	Free text
Do you have a local or national system (e.g., a data hub) that enables capturing rich metadata that can be reused later?	Free text
What kind of attribution would you like to see if your data is re-used?	Free text
Data consumer - Re-using data from public repositories	
Metadata needed for your analysis beyond standard checklist elements	Free text
Additional metadata from the wet lab (e.g. the "ENA Read Submission")	Free text
Additional metadata from the data analysis (e.g. assembly & annotation)	Free text
Metadata from standard checklists you would like to be mandatory	Free text

**ENA, European Nucleotide Archive; GenBank, NIH Genetic Sequence Database; Swiss-Prot, Manually Curated Protein Knowledgebase (UniProtKB/Swiss-Prot); PRIDE, PRoteomics IDentifications Database; PeptideAtlas, PeptideAtlas Proteomics Resource; MGnify, Microbiome Analysis Resource; Qiita, Microbiome Study Management Platform; PubMLST, Public Multi-Locus Sequence Typing Database; Enterobase, Bacterial Genomics and Population Structure Database; GISAIID, Global Initiative on Sharing All Influenza Data; PATRIC, Pathosystems Resource Integration Center; BioSamples, Biological Sample Metadata Database; ArrayExpress, Functional Genomics Data Repository; SRA, Sequence Read Archive.*

The participants were divided into three groups, focusing on 1) pathogen data from the Pathogens Portal, 2) microbiome studies via the example of bee microbiomes, and 3) general microbiome research. The results (n = 21 responses) for each quantifiable question from Table 1 were analyzed across these groups (Figure 1).

Figure 1 - Results of 21 responses to a metadata requirements survey. Each chart corresponds to specific questions for “Data producer - Submitting data to public repositories” from the survey, as outlined in Table 1. A: Organism group. B: Data types. C: Scientific application area. D: Purpose of data production. E: Public repository for data. F: Metadata exposure comfort level.

Responses from data producers

Responses from the perspective of data producers who submit their data to public repositories revealed a diverse range of microorganisms and data types, with a predominance of bacteria and a preference for metagenomics and genomic isolates (Figures 1A and 1B). The scientific areas covered were evenly split between health and environmental fields (Figure 1C). The primary purposes of data production were community profiling and strain typing and clustering (Figure 1D). The European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) [6] was the most commonly used public repository (Figure 1E). Researchers expressed comfort in exposing both aggregated and sample-level information prior to publication, with a preference for aggregated data (Figure 1F). Sample-level metadata that researchers were willing to share for early discovery included, among others, type, subtype or lineage information, country, collection date, and contact information. Aggregated-level information included the number of samples, species, country, purpose of data generation, and contact information. In addition, checklists such as ENA Checklists and Minimum Information about any (x) Sequence (MIxS) [7] are being widely used, but access to contextual data from wet labs varied, with only some researchers having access to protocols

(not shown). Attribution preferences for data reuse included citations to original publications (if available) with accession numbers.

Responses from data consumers

From the perspective of data consumers, who reuse data from public repositories, the metadata needed for analysis, beyond standard checklist elements, included detailed information on collection sites, raw bioinformatics information, and specific habitat information. Additional metadata from wet labs and data analysis, such as PCR protocols, library preparation methods, and tool versions, were also desired. Metadata from standard checklists that researchers think should be mandatory included geographic location, sample type, host scientific name, gender, and age.

Overall, the study highlighted the importance of comprehensive metadata for both data producers and consumers. This emphasizes the need for standardized checklists and the importance of researchers being willing to share certain metadata prior to publication, in order to facilitate early discovery and collaboration.

Part II: Solutions for metadata improvement

While the first part of the workshop aimed to identify necessary metadata, the second part focused on how to enhance it. Mark Ibberson (Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics) introduced this topic with a discussion on the harmonization of clinical terms using the tool OntoMapper [8] through the presentation titled “Harmonisation of clinical terms using Ontomapper”. The tool maps clinical terms to standardized ontologies such as Logical Observation Identifiers, Names, and Codes (LOINC®) and Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine Clinical Terms (SNOMED CT), enabling integration of data across multiple projects like Endotarget (<https://endotargetproject.eu/>) and Hippocrates (<https://www.hippocrates-imi.eu/>). The talk also explored how Large Language Models (LLMs) improve concept mapping and concluded by stressing the vital role of tools like OntoMapper and Artificial Intelligence (AI) in accelerating accurate and interoperable clinical research.

The presentation was followed by a second group work session, where the objectives were to:

1. Identify common issues found in submitted metadata.
2. Discuss how we can improve the existing metadata situation.
3. Survey if participants have access to a local or national system (e.g., a data hub) that enables capturing rich metadata that can be reused later.

The participants were divided into three groups focusing on either pre-submission strategies to encourage better metadata submission (1 group), or post-submission techniques to expand and curate existing metadata (2 groups).

Response from pre-submission discussion

The pre-submission discussion centered on addressing the pervasive “lacking metadata problem”, which is considered non-specific to any particular fields or domains. The primary

objective was to explore strategies to encourage scientists to fill out metadata comprehensively before submission.

A key theme was the importance of engaging core facilities, e.g. sequencing centers, early so that scientists understand the value of metadata, and so complete it more accurately. Experiences from countries like Norway and Germany were highlighted as models, along with the need to show how good metadata increases visibility, reuse, and citation. Sharing success stories, particularly from COVID initiatives, and providing published references, can help to demonstrate and quantify tangible benefits and motivate better practices.

Participants suggested a pre-registration system where metadata is agreed upon at the proposal stage, making compliance easier, and reducing missing data. AI and automation tools such as MetaBuddy (unpublished) could further cut workload by generating metadata automatically, mapping ontologies, and assisting scientists. Incentives—recognition, rewards, FAIRness scores, and linking funding or publishing to quality metadata—were also considered effective motivators.

National systems like data hubs and training programs can support rich metadata capture and reuse, while promoting cultural change, so metadata is valued rather than seen as bureaucracy. Visibility of projects that reuse data, FAIR scoring systems, and ORCID badges can provide recognition. Training sequencing facilities and integrating metadata into SOPs was proposed as a softer alternative to strict enforcement.

In conclusion, early engagement, incentives, education, and AI support are central to improving metadata practices, thereby increasing data visibility, reuse, and collaboration.

Key points from pre-submission discussion:

- Early engagement with core facilities helps establish good metadata practices.
- Demonstrating benefits (visibility, reuse, citations) motivates scientists.
- Pre-registration and automation (AI tools) reduce workload and errors.
- Incentives and recognition encourage compliance with FAIR principles.
- National systems, training, and cultural change are needed for long-term impact.

Response from post-submission discussion

The discussions in the post-submission groups focused on strategies to improve metadata once it has been submitted to public repositories. These strategies encompass both the curation of submitted metadata and the enrichment with analysis-derived metadata, such as viral lineages or antimicrobial resistance (AMR) profiles. The overarching goal of these efforts is to enhance data discoverability, reusability, and to support cross-referencing and integration of microbial data across platforms.

Discussions focused on challenges in curating producer-submitted metadata, including inconsistency, incompleteness, and lack of standardization. Automation using controlled vocabularies and ontologies was seen as essential, though concerns were raised about the adequacy of existing ontologies. Tools like OntoMapper were highlighted for post-submission curation, while debate continued on whether curation responsibility should fall on producers or a central platform. Tracking changes and maintaining version history was emphasized as critical.

The group also addressed enrichment with analysis-derived metadata (e.g., lineage, serotype, AMR, taxonomy). These outputs are often absent from public archives or scattered across systems. Proposals included linking results back to original submissions, exporting in submission-ready formats, and creating feedback loops with domain-specific platforms (e.g., GISAID [9], EnteroBase [10]) via tools on user-friendly platforms like Galaxy [11].

Beyond their technical value, such enrichment activities can serve as one of the strongest incentives for data producers to share their data. When researchers can visualize their datasets in the context of others, gaining access to comparative analyses and broader scientific visibility, the perceived value of contribution increases. This can stimulate collaborations, lead to additional publications, and make databases more useful for public health institutions such as World Health Organization (WHO) or the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC). Furthermore, incentives for producers to update metadata were discussed, as few respond to requests to improve submissions. Questions arose around third-party curation, its visibility, and whether updates could override original records. Metadata versioning was seen as necessary for ensuring traceability.

AI was identified as a promising tool to check consistency and suggest ontology mappings before submission, and third-party platforms for simple term mapping were proposed to improve metadata quality and usability.

Key points from post-submission discussion:

- Metadata quality issues (inconsistency, incompleteness) require harmonization.
- Automation and tools (e.g., OntoMapper, AI) can support curation and ontology mapping.
- Analysis-derived metadata (lineage, AMR, taxonomy) should be linked back to original submissions.
- Incentives and versioning are needed to encourage producers and manage third-party updates.
- Feedback loops and third-party platforms could enhance metadata integration and usability.

Conclusion and key outcomes

The joint workshop of the ELIXIR Pathogen Data Focus Group and the ELIXIR Microbiome Community highlighted both the challenges and opportunities in mobilizing microbial data. Across discussions, participants emphasized that metadata remains the cornerstone of data reuse, yet is often incomplete, inconsistent, or siloed. Both pre-submission and post-submission strategies are needed: the former to encourage richer and more accurate metadata capture at the source, and the latter to curate, enrich, and integrate records across repositories. The workshop participants were mainly ELIXIR members, including bioinformaticians and data stewards, representing national nodes, research infrastructures, and community-driven data resources involved in microbial data management and sharing. As a consequence, the discussions primarily reflect infrastructure and data stewardship perspectives, with more limited input from primary data producers such as experimental researchers and clinicians. The slide deck including the presentations are published together with this report on Zenodo.

Key outcomes and recommendations:

- Metadata is central: Comprehensive, standardized metadata is essential for reuse, discovery, and interoperability.
- Pre-submission strategies: Early engagement, training, and pre-registration of metadata improve completeness and accuracy.
- Post-submission strategies: Curation, enrichment with analysis-derived metadata (e.g., AMR, lineage), and clear versioning enhance usability.
- Automation & AI: Tools can reduce workload, support ontology mapping, and enhance metadata consistency.
- Incentives & recognition: FAIRness scores, ORCID badges, and visibility of data reuse motivate better metadata practices.
- National & European infrastructures: Data hubs and coordinated systems are needed to capture, manage, and integrate rich metadata.
- Cross-community alignment: Stronger collaboration between pathogen and microbiome initiatives will advance a unified European approach.

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Code and data availability

The 1st group work results and code used to the figures presented in this report are stored on a dedicated GitHub repository (https://github.com/bebatut/mobilizing_microbial_data_elixir_ahm_2025).

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